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The Development of a Local History Digital Module Based on the Local Wisdom of the *Andingingi* Ritual

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Abstract

This study aims to: (1) identify the specifications of a local history digital module based on the *Andingingi* local wisdom ritual in enhancing students' understanding; (2) evaluate the feasibility and practicality of the module; and (3) examine its effectiveness in improving students' comprehension of local history. The study employed a Research and Development (R&D) approach utilizing the ADDIE model and was conducted at SMAN 6 Bulukumba and SMA Islam Athirah Bukit Baruga. The findings indicate that: (1) the developed digital module integrates various multimedia elements, including images, videos, and interactive features, to support learning engagement; (2) the module demonstrates a high level of feasibility, with scores of 4.75 (content) and 4.70 (media), both categorized as "highly feasible." Additionally, large-scale validation results show mean scores of 4.87 from teachers and 4.70 from students, further confirming its validity and practicality; and (3) the module is effective in improving students' understanding of local history. This is evidenced by the N-Gain results, where students in the experimental class at SMAN 6 Bulukumba achieved a higher gain score (0.559) compared to the control class (0.403). Similarly, at SMA Islam Athirah Bukit Baruga, the experimental class attained a gain score of 0.647, exceeding that of the control class (0.420).

Keywords: *Andingingi* Ritual; Digital Module; Local History Understanding.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Research Background

The era of globalization has brought significant changes to various aspects of Indonesian society, including in the fields of education and the preservation of local cultural values. The flow of information and technological advancements have made the younger generation increasingly familiar with global culture, which can shift their understanding and appreciation of local wisdom passed down through generations (Siregar et al., 2024). This situation has sparked concerns regarding the fading of national identity due to the strong influence of foreign cultures.

History education plays a crucial role in shaping character and national identity through a deep understanding of past events that have shaped society (Rulianto, 2018). Within the scope of national

education, history education does not merely focus on conveying information about the past but also aims to foster historical awareness and the values of local wisdom (Juliyati, 2021). Local history education is particularly important as it provides a more concrete and relevant context for students in understanding the historical dynamics occurring in their immediate surroundings.

According to Syahputra et al. (2020), history learning becomes meaningful when connected to the students' local context through an introduction to local events in their region. This aligns with the view of Hidayati et al. (2020), who argue that local history education contributes to building national identity by internalizing the values of local wisdom found in the students' surrounding environment. Furthermore, (Dienaputra, 2020) emphasizes that local history education can foster *historical awareness*. Students can understand that historical events actually took place around them, not merely as stories of the past (Asmara, 2019).

However, in reality, history education at the high school level still faces a number of challenges. To date, the learning process remains dominated by conventional, teacher-centered approaches and a reliance on national textbooks, resulting in suboptimal integration of local history content. This situation aligns with the findings of Sinurat et al. (2025), who state that one of the main obstacles in history education in Indonesia is the suboptimal use of local historical sources, which could fundamentally deepen students' understanding of the historical dynamics in their regions. Furthermore, the lack of innovative and interactive learning media also poses a barrier to creating engaging and meaningful history lessons. Yet, in this digital age, students are already familiar with technology and digital media. According to Putri (2024), the use of digital learning media has been proven to enhance students' motivation and understanding of historical content.

One region with a wealth of local wisdom that can be integrated into history education is Bulukumba Regency, South Sulawesi. This area boasts various traditions and rituals that reflect the identity of its people, one of which is the *Andingingi* ritual (Arumingtyas et al., 2023). According to Nurfadillah et al. (2023), the *Andingingi* ritual is a traditional ceremony of the Kajang community performed as a form of respect and a request for permission from the ruler of the universe before carrying out agricultural activities or other important activities. Behind this procession lie noble values that teach balance between humans, God, fellow humans, and the universe (Umajjah et al., 2021).

However, with the passage of time, understanding and practice of the *Andingingi* ritual have begun to fade among the younger generation. Referring to Nurdin (2020) findings, this phenomenon is attributed to several factors, including: 1) the insufficient integration of local wisdom values into the formal education curriculum; 2) a lack of engaging and contextually relevant learning materials related to local wisdom; and 3) a lack of awareness among students regarding the importance of preserving local culture as a fundamental element of their identity.

Advances in digital technology offer extensive opportunities to develop learning materials that are more interactive, inspiring, and aligned with the characteristics of Generation Z students (Prensky, 2022). Digital modules present a promising alternative for delivering local wisdom content in a more dynamic and relevant manner to meet students' needs. Research by Widodo & Wahyudin (2021) indicates that the use of digital modules has been proven to significantly enhance learning effectiveness and student motivation. Through digital modules, the values of the *Andingingi* ritual can be presented in a more attractive format, supported by comprehensive multimedia integration, including documentary videos, images, animations, and interactive features that can enhance students' active engagement (Mayer & Moreno, 2023).

³ The development of a digital local history module based on the *Andingingi* ritual holds high relevance to the characteristics of high school students who are already familiar with digital technology. This aligns with the digital native concept proposed by Prensky (2022), which suggests that today's younger generation has grown and developed within a digital technology environment. Therefore, the use of a digital module can serve as a bridge between local history learning content and the learning preferences of students who favor digital media. Furthermore, the development of this digital local history module based on the local wisdom of the *Andingingi* ritual is consistent with the spirit of Merdeka Belajar (Freedom to Learn) and the Merdeka Curriculum, which emphasize contextual, meaningful, and student-centered learning (Kemendikbudristek, 2022). Through this approach, students are expected to develop a holistic understanding of local wisdom values and apply them within the context of daily life. Moreover, the development of this module supports efforts toward the preservation and revitalization of local culture through formal education, which serves as a vital strategy in maintaining the sustainability of cultural heritage amidst the currents of globalization (UNESCO, 2022).

³ Given this background, the development of a digital history module that integrates the local wisdom of the *Andingingi* ritual is crucial for enhancing high school students' understanding of local history. This digital tool is designed as an innovative and interactive learning medium that combines modern technology with authentic local historical content. The development of this module is projected to contribute to four main aspects. First, it deepens students' understanding of local history and culture through an engaging learning process. Second, it preserves and passes on the values of local wisdom to the younger generation; third, it provides an alternative learning medium for teachers in teaching local history; and fourth, it serves as a model for the development of local history education that can be applied in other schools.

1.2. Literature Review

Etymologically, local wisdom consists of two words: wisdom and local. Other terms for local wisdom include local wisdom, local knowledge, and local genius (Shufa et al., 2018). Meanwhile, according to Chaiphar et al. (2013), local wisdom is a way of life passed down from one generation to the next in the form of religion, culture, or customs that are common within a society's social system. Local wisdom can be viewed as a national identity, particularly in the Indonesian context, where it enables local wisdom to transform across cultures, ultimately giving rise to national cultural values. In Indonesia, local wisdom is a philosophy and way of life manifested in various aspects of life (social and economic values, architecture, health, environmental management, and so on) (Romadi & Kurniawan, 2017).

Local wisdom is the result of the behaviors and practices of communities that have evolved since prehistoric times, and serves as a positive guide for interactions—both with nature and with fellow human beings. These values stem from customs, religious teachings, and the wisdom of ancestors that have naturally taken shape within a community. In the context of modern life, local wisdom acts as a filter against the rapid flow of globalization, while also serving as a foundation for the development of moral character. Thus, local wisdom encourages people to act based on awareness, responsibility, and self-control (Wagiran, 2012).

1.2.1. Digital Module

A module is a type of learning resource designed to support the learning process. As a learning resource, modules are organized systematically and engagingly so that students can study the material independently (Kurniawan & Kuswandi, 2021). A module can be defined as instructional material based on learning principles and developed by teachers in a comprehensive and step-by-step manner (Tomlinson, 2023). Modules are developed systematically, comprising an introduction, content, main material, and conclusion arranged in sequential order (Richlin, 2023).

In general, both modules and e-modules are types of instructional materials widely used in learning activities. An e-module is a self-directed learning resource that is systematically designed and presented in digital form (Zufahmi et al., 2025). It contains structured content, learning activities, and assessment tools to evaluate the success of knowledge transfer and the level of mastery of the material presented. With e-modules, educators have greater opportunities to create diverse learning resources not limited to text and images but can also include interactive content and videos, whether created in house or sourced from available platforms such as YouTube.

7 The advantage of digital modules is their ability to present content and practice questions in various formats not only text but also supplemented with images and videos that support the learning process (Farokhah et al., 2025). Additionally, digital modules serve as tools for creating engaging learning experiences (Ramdiah et al., 2026).

A module is a type of instructional material that can make the learning process more effective (Sibley & Ostafichuk, 2023). A module contains a series of learning activities organized systematically, along with clearly and specifically formulated learning objectives, enabling students to learn independently (Famulaqih & Lukman, 2024). This aligns with the view of Setiyawan & Syamsuddin Nurul Iman (2026), who state that digital modules can offer relatively greater value compared to conventional teaching. The development of instructional modules aims to provide learning tools that can guide teachers in conducting the teaching-learning process (Roblyer et al., 2024). In practice, teachers have the freedom to select or modify teaching modules provided by the government to suit student characteristics or to independently develop teaching modules tailored to student needs (Salsabilla et al., 2023). The development of instructional materials in the form of digital modules aligns with developments and innovations in the field of education and is in line with the current digital era (Leo Agung & Akhyar, 2019).

1.2.2. Local Wisdom of the *Andingingi* Ritual

Every region has its own unique traditions that serve as a cultural identity and distinguish it from other regions. These traditions have been passed down from generation to generation, reflecting the richness of our ancestral heritage. In Indonesia, this diversity of traditions can still be found from the westernmost to the easternmost parts of the country, from Sabang to Merauke. The preservation of these traditions is crucial because they constitute an invaluable part of the nation's cultural heritage and can serve as a foundation for the development and advancement of the nation's culture. South Sulawesi, as one of Indonesia's regions, boasts a rich tapestry of cultures and traditions rooted in the presence of several major ethnic groups, such as the Bugis, Makassar, Mandar, and Toraja peoples (Bungatang et al., 2024).

Among these tribes, there is one community with unique cultural characteristics and sacred values: the Kajang tribe. This tribe inhabits the rural areas of Kajang Subdistrict, Bulukumba Regency, South Sulawesi. The Kajang people hold a fundamental belief that their territorial area, known as Tanah Toa, is a sacred legacy from their ancestors, entrusted to them with the mandate to be continuously safeguarded and preserved (Darmapoetra, 2014).

The Kajang people are known for their distinctive tradition of wearing black clothing. The color black holds sacred significance, particularly when someone enters the territory of the *Ammatoa* the title given to the local traditional leader. For the Kajang people, black symbolizes the principle of equality in various aspects of life, including the practice of a simple lifestyle. For the Kajang people, when someone enters the Kajang traditional territory, they are required to wear all-black clothing as a form of respect for tradition. The color black is interpreted as a symbol of equality in all aspects of life, including living a simple life. There is no difference in value between one shade of black and another, as all are considered equal. Furthermore, the color black also represents strength, equality of status, and justice for every individual in the presence of the Creator (Nurfadillah et al., 2023).

The most essential aspect of the Kajang people's culture is their deep respect for nature. The Kajang people firmly believe that when humans are able to protect and care for their natural surroundings, nature will in turn provide them with protection and blessings. This view reflects the principle of balance between humans and the environment, which also serves as the cultural identity of the Kajang people in fostering a harmonious relationship with nature. With this in mind, the Kajang tribe has a local tradition of preserving the natural environment. This local tradition of the Kajang tribe is called the *Andingingi* ritual. Koentjaraningrat describes a ritual as a system of activation or a series of actions governed by customs or laws applicable within a society, related to specific recurring events that typically occur within that society (Rumahuru, 2018).

The *Andingingi* ritual is a traditional ceremony that serves as a form of reverence and a plea for nature and all its inhabitants to remain serene, peaceful, and safe. During the ceremony, all participants are required to wear distinctive black attire that holds sacred significance for the Kajang people. This ritual serves as a means for the community to offer prayers, seeking blessings, protection, and safety for all of God's creations on Earth. The philosophical values within this tradition reflect an expression of gratitude to God for His gifts, as well as demonstrate the close interdependence between humans and nature in the life of the Kajang indigenous community (Hidayat et al., 2022). Local traditions in South Sulawesi are manifestations of a value system that governs the social life of the community and serves as a guide for interacting with others and the environment (Iswatiningsih, 2019).

1.2.3. Understanding Local History

History consists of events that occurred in the past and encompasses various aspects, such as economic, social, and cultural dimensions (Burke, 2019). In this regard, history plays a vital role in human life as it can serve as a benchmark for navigating the future (Ware, 2020). Therefore, history learning can take place in various settings, both in and out of school (Haydn & Stephen, 2021). However, ideal history learning should be conducted in schools with the aim of enabling students to develop critical thinking skills and gain a solid understanding of history (Levstik & Barton, 2022).

History education is also crucial for fostering a sense of nationalism and preserving national identity. However, there remains a perception that history lessons are boring for some students. This results in a low level of understanding of history, particularly local history, because the material taught focuses primarily on national history without being balanced by local historical content (Agustina & Amboro, 2019). History education plays a strategic role in developing and honing students' abilities related to historical understanding, historical thinking, and historical awareness (Bunari et al., 2023).

Understanding local history is a key aspect of history education that focuses on the events, figures, and cultures that have developed in a specific region. According to Sayer (2026), local history not only addresses major events at the national level but also highlights the social, cultural, and economic dynamics of the local community. By studying local history, students can understand the connection between national events and the lives of people in their surroundings, making history feel more accessible, relevant, and contextual (Kuwoto & Saputra, 2024). The educational value of local history learning lies in its ability to provide students with in-depth knowledge and understanding regarding their own identity, the presence of culture in their surroundings, and human interaction with the culture where they live (Taneo & Ly, 2019).

An understanding of local history also helps students develop a sense of belonging to their regional cultural identity. By learning about local wisdom, traditions, and regional historical figures, students will come to better appreciate their cultural heritage (Filina, 2025). Local wisdom values are important cultural assets that reflect the identity, values, and historical experiences of a community (Apdelmi et al., 2025). Local wisdom not only plays a role in enriching learning materials but also in strengthening students' cultural identity and enhancing their resilience against the homogenizing effects of globalization (Morales do Nascimento et al., 2022). This awareness is crucial for building a national character rooted in one's own history and culture, while also preventing students from developing an apathetic attitude toward their social environment (Ratih et al., 2025). In an educational context, an understanding of local history can be developed through various approaches, such as field studies, interviews with historical figures, analysis of local historical documents, and the use of available primary sources (Syahputra et al., 2020).

An understanding of ⁸ local history also plays a role in strengthening awareness of cultural diversity and social dynamics at the local level (Putra Yasa et al., 2025). Through the study of local history, students can understand how interactions between individuals and groups shape the traditions, values, and norms that prevail in society (Mbatha & Moreeng, 2024). This awareness is crucial for fostering attitudes of tolerance and respect for differences, particularly within pluralistic societies. Thus, local history serves as a strategic tool in multicultural education (LePoire, 2025).

In addition, learning local history can encourage students' active engagement in the learning process (Yuan et al., 2026). By utilizing the surrounding environment as a learning resource, students can conduct direct observations, interview community leaders, and explore historical sites (Oxendine, 2026). These activities not only enhance conceptual understanding but also develop basic research skills. Therefore, understanding local history involves cognitive, affective, and psychomotor dimensions that are mutually integrated within the learning process.

2. METHODS

¹ This study adopted a research and development (R&D) approach utilizing the ADDIE model (Figure 1), which encompasses five systematic phases: analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation.

This approach was employed to ensure that the developed instructional module is grounded in robust theoretical foundations, aligned with sound pedagogical principles, and rigorously evaluated in terms of its validity, practicality, and effectiveness.

1 Figure 1. Steps of the ADDIE Model Development and Research
(Source: Authors, 2026)

2.1. Research Design

1 The ADDIE framework served as the foundational model for the development and validation of the digital history module. The process was systematically organized into five phases as follows:

1. Analysis Phase: This phase involved identifying curriculum requirements, student characteristics, and cultural relevance through teacher interviews, classroom observations, and document analysis.
2. Design Phase: Learning objectives were formulated, instructional materials were selected, and assessment instruments were developed in alignment with historical content and local wisdom.
3. Development Phase: A prototype of the module was developed by integrating the local wisdom of the *Andingingi* ritual, followed by expert validation involving content, media, and instrument specialists.
4. Implementation Phase: The module was implemented through classroom trials in two schools to examine its usability and student engagement.
5. Evaluation Phase: Both formative and summative evaluations were conducted to determine the overall effectiveness of the module.

2.2. Participants and Research Locations

This study was conducted at two high schools in South Sulawesi Province: SMA Negeri 6 Bulukumba and SMA Islam Athirah Bukit Baruga. Participants included 116 tenth-grade students (64 students from SMA Negeri 6 Bulukumba and 52 students from SMA Islam Athirah Bukit Baruga) as well as two teachers who facilitated classroom learning. These schools were selected purposively due to their involvement in local cultural integration programs.

2.3. Data Collection Procedures

Data was collected through three main procedures:

1. Expert Validation: This procedure aimed to establish the validity of the module through evaluations conducted by three expert groups, namely subject matter experts, media experts, and instrument experts.
2. Field Testing: This stage was carried out during classroom implementation to assess user experience, particularly in terms of usability and acceptance among teachers and students.
3. Effectiveness Testing: A pre-test and post-test design was employed to examine the impact of the module on students' history comprehension skills.

2.4. Instrument

Three instruments were developed and validated for data collection:

1. Expert Validation Sheet: This instrument comprised 10 items for each evaluation conducted by subject matter experts and media experts, measured using a five-point Likert scale (1 = poor to 5 = excellent).
2. Usability Questionnaire: This instrument included 10 Likert-scale items designed to assess content appropriateness, visual presentation, ease of use, and perceived benefits, with a reliability coefficient of Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.88$.
3. Critical Thinking Test: This instrument consisted of 15 multiple-choice items aimed at measuring students' critical thinking skills.

All instruments were subjected to expert review and pilot testing to establish content validity and ensure reliability prior to data collection.

2.5. Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics:

1. Validation Results: These were presented as percentages reflecting the mean scores assigned by the expert evaluators.
2. Practicality Test: Descriptive statistics were employed to determine mean scores, which were subsequently interpreted using categorical criteria (i.e., Excellent, Good, Fair, Poor, and Unacceptable).
3. Effectiveness Tests: The effectiveness of the module was assessed through pre-test and post-test comparisons, with learning gains analyzed using the N-Gain formula:

$$\text{N-Gain} = \frac{\text{Skor Posttest} - \text{Skor Pretest}}{\text{Skor Ideal} - \text{Skor Pretest}}$$

The resulting N-Gain scores were classified into three categories: high (> 0.7), moderate ($0.3-0.7$), and low (< 0.3). In addition, normality and homogeneity tests were conducted to ensure the appropriateness and reliability of the data for further statistical analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings in direct relation to the research questions outlined in the Introduction. The results are systematically organized to demonstrate (a) the validity of the developed history teaching module, (b) its practicality during classroom implementation, and (c) its effectiveness in improving students' understanding of local history. Each subsection corresponds to specific datasets obtained through the instruments described in the Methodology section. The first set of findings (Section 3.1) addresses the validity of the module, which was evaluated using an expert validation sheet consisting of 10 items rated on a five-point Likert scale. The second set of findings (Section 3.2) focuses on the module's practicality, assessed through questionnaires administered to both students and teachers, comprising 10 Likert-scale items measuring content appropriateness, visual presentation, ease of use, and perceived benefits. The third set of findings (Section 3.3) examines the module's effectiveness, based on students' pre-test and post-test scores derived from a 15-item multiple-choice test on local history comprehension. This structured approach ensures that all reported findings are explicitly aligned with the research questions and are derived from systematically validated instruments.

3.1. Validation Result of the Module

The history module, which was developed with a focus on the local wisdom of the *Andingingi* ritual, was evaluated by two groups of experts: subject matter experts and media experts, as shown in Figure 2 & Figure 3.

Figure 2. Diagram of Material Validation Results

Based on Figure 2, the validation results for the digital module's content yielded an average score of 4.75, placing it in the "Highly Feasible" category. This indicates that the content developed for the *Andingingi* Ritual local wisdom module can be used to enhance understanding of local history.

Figure 3. Media Validation Results Diagram

Based on Figure 3, the media validation results for the digital module achieved an average score of 4.70 and fell into the “Highly Feasible” category. This indicates that the developed digital module on the local wisdom of the *Andingingi* Ritual can be used to enhance understanding of local history.

3.2. Practicality of the Module in Learning Activities

The module’s practicality was evaluated through limited and large-scale trials conducted in two different schools: SMA Negeri 6 Bulukumba and SMA Islam Athirah Bukit Baruga, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Summarizing the practicality test results of the module across the two schools:

School	Number of Respondents	Average Score	Threshold Score	Category
SMA Negeri 6 Bulukumba	64	4,76	3,40	Highly Feasible
SMA Islam Athirah Bukit Baruga	52	4,73	3,40	Highly Feasible

Table 1 presents the results of the practicality test of the history teaching module oriented toward the local wisdom of the *Andingingi* Ritual, based on student responses from two senior high schools. Overall, the findings indicate that the module demonstrates a high level of practicality within both educational contexts. At SMAN 6 Bulukumba, responses from 64 students yielded a mean score of 4.76, which falls within the “Highly Feasible” category and exceeds the established threshold score of 3.40. Similarly, SMA Islam Athirah Bukit Baruga reported a mean score of 4.73 based on 52 student responses, further supporting the module’s practical applicability. These findings confirm the module’s strong practical value and indicate a high level of user acceptance across different school settings. Moreover, the results suggest that the module holds considerable potential to enhance students’ understanding of local history (Syahputra et al., 2020; Putra Yasa et al., 2025; LePoire, 2025; Yuan et al., 2026).

3.3. The Effectiveness of the Module in Enhancing Local History Understanding

Table 2 presents the effectiveness test result of the Module in enhancing local history understanding, based on a pre-test and post-test evaluation.

Table 2. The effectiveness test results of the *Andingingi* Ritual module

Test Type	Pre-Test Score (Average)	Post-Test Score (Average)	N-Gain Score	N-Gain %	Effectiveness Category
Local History Understanding	54	77	0,507	50,7	Moderately Effective

The presented data regarding the effectiveness of the *Andingingi* Ritual history module in enhancing students' local history understanding highlights a significant improvement, from a pre-test average score of 54 to a post-test average of 77. This reflects a clear enhancement in students' local history comprehension performance. This substantial improvement resulted in an N-Gain score of 0.507 with a percentage gain of 50.7%, categorizing the module's effectiveness as "Moderately Effective" according to educational intervention benchmarks (Sukarelawan et al., 2024).

Based on the research results presented, these findings align with the three primary foundations of digital learning theory: cognitivism, constructivism, and behaviorism. Viewed from the perspective of cognitivism, the successful use of this digital module is influenced by the structured and systematic presentation of materials, which integrates relevant elements of text, imagery, and narration. This presentation facilitates students in processing and retaining information related to the local wisdom of the *Andingingi* Ritual (Sinaga et al., 2024; Harefa et al., 2024; Ibda, 2015; Ismaimuza, 2025; Widayanthi et al., 2024; Artawijaya & Saptiari, 2023). Furthermore, based on constructivism theory, students in the experimental class were provided with opportunities to independently construct their understanding through the exploration of the digital module's content. This process encouraged active student engagement in the learning process, resulting in a deeper and more meaningful understanding. This finding is consistent with the N-Gain values, which were higher in the experimental class compared to the control class (Haryanto, 2020; Asfar et al., 2019). Meanwhile, from the perspective of behaviorism theory, the digital module provides stimuli in the form of practice exercises, interactive quizzes, and immediate feedback that serve to reinforce positive learning behaviors. These stimuli encourage students to maintain and improve their understanding of local history. The improvement observed through the difference in N-Gain values between the experimental and control classes demonstrates that this positive reinforcement operates effectively within the context of digital-based history learning (Azzahra et al., 2025; Damayanti, 2023).

Furthermore, the results of this study also indicate that the use of digital modules not only influences the improvement of knowledge regarding historical events but also has the potential to instill historical, cultural, and local wisdom values in students. Through this learning process, students are expected to appreciate ancestral cultural heritage while simultaneously strengthening their national identity. The utilization of digital technology allows historical material to be presented in a more engaging, interactive, and contextual manner, thereby accommodating various student learning styles. This approach also serves as an effort to address the challenges of 21st-century learning, where mastery of digital literacy is a crucial

skill for students. Therefore, the integration of digital modules into history education is not only relevant for improving learning outcomes but also holds a strategic role in shaping a younger generation that possesses historical awareness and a commitment to local wisdom values. (Abd Majid, 2024; Nugroho Yulianto & Olivia, 2023; Kumiawan & Kuswandi, 2021; Sibley & Ostafichuk, 2023).

3.4. Integration of *Andingingi* Ritual Local Wisdom into History Education

The integration of *Andingingi* Ritual local wisdom into History Education is visual supported by the instructional components shown in Figure 4(a), (b), and (c).

(a)

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PETUNJUK PENGGUNAAN MODUL

A. Petunjuk Bagi Peserta Didik

1. Bacalah dan pahami terlebih dahulu tujuan pembelajaran yang harus dicapai oleh peserta didik.
- 2.ikuti petunjuk yang terdapat dalam setiap penjelasan materi.
3. Setelah selesai mempelajari kearifan lokal, maka dibuktikan dengan terapan.
4. Setelah selesai mempelajari mata bahasan maka berdiskusi dengan guru pembimbing.
5. Setelah memahami materi, cobalah menyelesaikan soal-soal uji kompetensi dan lakukan hasil pengajaran Anda dengan guru pembimbing terlan dibuktikan.

B. Petunjuk Bagi Guru

1. Bacalah dan pahami terlebih dahulu tujuan modul yang akan dibelajarkan.
2. Bedah capaian dan pemahaman yang harus dicapai oleh peserta didik mengenai modul yang digunakan dalam pembelajaran.
3. Guru dapat membantu peserta didik dalam memahami materi kearifan lokal ritual andingingi.
4. Guru dapat membantu peserta didik dalam menyelesaikan soal-soal uji kompetensi dalam modul.

PETA KONSEP

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    graph LR
      A[Kearifan Lokal Ritual Andingingi] --> B[Ritual Andingingi]
      A --> C[Proses Ritual Andingingi]
      A --> D[Makna Ritual Andingingi]
  
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INFORMASI UMUM

A. Identitas Modul

Nama Penyusunan	Syafiqul Hidayat, S.Pd.
Revisi/Revisi	0001

B. Capaian Pembelajaran

Pengetahuan dan keterampilan yang harus dikuasai oleh peserta didik dalam mempelajari kearifan lokal ritual andingingi.

KOMPONEN INTI

A. Tujuan Pembelajaran

- Peserta didik memahami kearifan lokal ritual andingingi sebagai kearifan lokal.
- Peserta didik mampu menjelaskan proses ritual andingingi.
- Peserta didik mampu menjelaskan makna ritual andingingi.

B. Pemahaman Bermakna

- Peserta didik mampu memahami kearifan lokal ritual andingingi.
- Peserta didik mampu menjelaskan makna kearifan lokal ritual andingingi.

C. Kegiatan Pembelajaran

Pengetahuan dan keterampilan yang harus dikuasai oleh peserta didik dalam mempelajari kearifan lokal ritual andingingi.

Perencanaan	Kejelasan Guru	Alokasi Waktu
Identifikasi		

(b)

URAIAN MATERI

A. Definisi Lokal Wisdom

Local wisdom is a form of practical wisdom that is deeply rooted in the local culture and environment. It is a form of knowledge that is passed down from generation to generation and is often used to solve problems and make decisions in a community.

Local wisdom is a form of practical wisdom that is deeply rooted in the local culture and environment. It is a form of knowledge that is passed down from generation to generation and is often used to solve problems and make decisions in a community.

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B. Proses Ritual Andingingi

The process of the Andingingi ritual involves several steps, including preparation, the main ritual, and the closing. The ritual is performed by a community leader and is often accompanied by traditional music and dance.

The process of the Andingingi ritual involves several steps, including preparation, the main ritual, and the closing. The ritual is performed by a community leader and is often accompanied by traditional music and dance.

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C. Maksud Ritual Andingingi

The purpose of the Andingingi ritual is to strengthen the community and to seek blessings from the ancestors. It is a form of spiritual practice that is deeply rooted in the local culture and environment.

The purpose of the Andingingi ritual is to strengthen the community and to seek blessings from the ancestors. It is a form of spiritual practice that is deeply rooted in the local culture and environment.

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(c)

Rangkuman

The Andingingi ritual is a form of spiritual practice that is deeply rooted in the local culture and environment. It is a form of knowledge that is passed down from generation to generation and is often used to solve problems and make decisions in a community.

The Andingingi ritual is a form of spiritual practice that is deeply rooted in the local culture and environment. It is a form of knowledge that is passed down from generation to generation and is often used to solve problems and make decisions in a community.

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LAMPIRAN

A. LAMPIRAN BERGANDA

1. Menentukan latar belakang ritual Andingingi berdasarkan uraian.
2. Menjelaskan makna ritual Andingingi berdasarkan uraian.
3. Menjelaskan makna ritual Andingingi berdasarkan uraian.
4. Menjelaskan makna ritual Andingingi berdasarkan uraian.

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Biografi Penulis

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Figure 4. The Integration of *Andingingi* Ritual Local Wisdom into History Education

The integration of the *Andingingi* ritual local wisdom into the history module is underpinned by a pedagogical framework that emphasizes culturally relevant local wisdom. For instance, the designed digital module features a structured format consisting of introductory, core, and closing sections. Figure 4(a), representing the introductory section, includes the foreword, table of contents, list of figures, glossary, general information, and core components. Figure 4(b), representing the core section, comprises the local wisdom of the *Andingingi* ritual, the ritual procession, and the symbolic meanings of the *Andingingi* ritual. Lastly, Figure 4(c), representing the closing section, includes a summary, practice exercises, evaluation, references, and the author's biography.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The researcher has developed a digital history module based on the local wisdom of the *Andingingi* ritual by integrating various software and applications, such as Microsoft Word, Canva, and Flipbook, to create an engaging and interactive history learning experience centered on *Andingingi* ritual content. The development process employed the ADDIE model, encompassing the stages of Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation. Consequently, the digital module serves as an effective learning resource to support history education, particularly in efforts to enhance students' understanding of local history.

The digital history module based on the local wisdom of the *Andingingi* ritual is valid, practical, and feasible for use in the history learning process and for improving students' local history comprehension, based on evaluations from material and media experts, teachers, and students. This is supported by validation results, which yielded an average score of 4.75 from material experts and 4.70 from media experts, both falling into the "Highly Feasible" category. The feasibility test by history teachers achieved an average score of 4.87 (Highly Feasible). Furthermore, limited-scale testing with students resulted in an average score of 4.60, while wide-scale testing yielded an average of 4.70, both categorized as "Highly Feasible."

The effectiveness of the digital history module in enhancing the local history understanding of high school students is evidenced by the N-Gain test results. At SMAN 6 Bulukumba, the experimental class achieved an N-Gain score of 0.559, which is higher than the control class's score of 0.403. Similarly, at SMA Islam Athirah Bukit Baruga, the experimental class obtained an N-Gain score of 0.647, surpassing the control class's score of 0.420. Therefore, these findings prove to be relevant to digital learning theories—namely cognitivism, constructivism, and behaviorism—which emphasize the importance of structured material presentation, active student engagement in knowledge construction, and positive reinforcement through stimuli and feedback within the learning process.

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Ethics and Consent

This study was conducted in accordance with institutional ethical standards for research involving human participants (British Educational Research Association, 2018). Prior to data collection, ethical approval was

obtained from the Research Ethics Committee of Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta (approval number: 18/DST/UN34.14/B/PT.01.04/2026 and 18/DST/UN34.14/B/PT.01.04/2026), with official permission granted by SMAN 6 Bulukumba and SMA Islam Athirah Bukit Baruga (approval number: 421.3/024/UPT-SMAN 6 BLK/DISDIK/2026 and 013/SMA-SIA/BB/DP/V/2026).

Given that the participants were secondary school students (ages 16-17), written informed consent was obtained from parents/guardians and the school authorities. Additionally, children provided verbal assent before participation, and they were informed, in an age-appropriate manner, that their participation was voluntary, and they could withdraw from the study at any time.

All recruited participants were informed of these details and assured that their data would remain confidential, anonymized, and solely used for academic purposes. Participants were also informed that non-participation or withdrawal from the study would result in no negative consequences.

Verbal assent from the children and written consent from the parents were used to ensure that the children understood the study and felt comfortable with all aspects of participation (Mitchell & George, 2022; O'Hara et al., 2022)

Clinical Trial Registration

Not applicable.

Competing Interest

The authors declare no competing interests related to this study.

Author Contributions (CRediT taxonomy)

Syahrul Hidayat – Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft.

Risky Setiawan - Methodology, Formal Analysis, Validation, Writing – Review & Editing.

Hadi Wuloyo - Investigation, Data Curation

Pina Dhea Tafana - Investigation, Resources

Ines Alifah Wachidatun Chasanah - Formal Analysis, Visualization

Feriyansyah - Investigation, Visualization

Fransiskus Carbinsius Sabar - Validation, Writing – Review & Editing

Cindi Kristiani Alemoka - Resources, Data Curation

Putra Ramadhan - Resources, Supervision

Popon Aryani Sapitri - Conceptualization, Supervision, Funding Acquisition

Data Availability Statement

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